

Project Title	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud for the Netherlands
Project Acronym	SSHOC-NL
Funder	Dutch Research Council (NWO)
Grant	National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Infrastructure
File Number	184.036.020
Start Date of Project	2024-01-01
Duration of Project	60 months
Project Website	https://sshoc.nl/

SSHOC-NL T4.2 2024-D03:

Overview of Existing Data Discovery Mechanisms and Future Directions for (Common) Search

Workstream	FAIR (#4)
Task	Integrating microservices to increase data FAIRness (#4.2)
Author(s)	Ricarda Braukmann https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6383-7148 Jetze Touber https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4532-1273
Contributor(s)	Jacco van Ossenbruggen https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7748-4715 Andre Valdestilhas https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0079-2533 Angelica Maineri https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6978-5278
Date	2025-05-26
Version	V1.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15517066
Distribution	Public
Licence	CC-BY 4.0

Summary

One of the focus points of SSHOC-NL Task 4.2 (subtask 3) is to improve data discovery in the (Dutch) SSH domain. Supporting researchers in finding relevant datasets for reuse is an important ambition that both ODISSEI and CLARIAH share. This deliverable is meant as a starting point to summarize the data discovery efforts ODISSEI and CLARIAH have already invested in. It also provides an outlook into future collaborative developments that can be conducted within the SSHOC-NL project.

First, this deliverable briefly introduces the variety of data available in various Dutch SSH repositories. We continue to discuss insights on how researchers find and reuse data, in particular, based on the findings from a study conducted in SSHOC-NL Task 2.3 on the findability of cultural heritage datasets.

Then, we describe the current status of the data discovery portals that CLARIAH and ODISSEI have been developing to enable researchers to find relevant metadata from different sources in a central catalog. In particular, we discuss the current status of the ODISSEI Portal and the CLARIAH FAIRy registry. We review their metadata requirements, enrichments, and FAIR assessments and present the current user interfaces and the options for harvesting harmonized metadata.

Finally, this deliverable finishes with an outlook on the future directions within SSHOC-NL to further develop the available data discovery infrastructure, building on what is already available at CLARIAH and ODISSEI. Next to maintaining the available infrastructure to ensure that the services run smoothly for the community, enrichments of metadata and FAIR assessments are identified as two areas where ODISSEI and CLARIAH can learn from each other's existing implementation. This exchange can lead to a higher quality and harmonization of metadata available to users in both catalogs.

SSHOC-NL further provides a unique opportunity to align the available infrastructures, striving for a close collaboration on issues that span the entire domain. One such issue is the management of access to sensitive data through secure analysis environments. Analyzing

sensitive data (i.e. data which needs special protection due to privacy concerns or copyright restrictions) is an important common challenge that can be addressed through the SSHOC-NL collaboration by providing a standardized workflow, connecting the data discovery portals with available secure analysis environments through the so-called Data Access Broker (DAB). Further developing the DAB and harmonizing workflows for sensitive data is hence identified as an important element of the SSHOC-NL work for the coming period.

Introduction

One of the focus points of SSHOC-NL Task 4.2 is to improve data discovery in the (Dutch) SSH domain. While available datasets can theoretically be found in various ways and through multiple data catalogs, it remains challenging for researchers to easily and quickly find existing data that matches their requirements. Catalogs work differently, and available information about the datasets is typically not harmonized or connected across sources.

In this first deliverable of Task 4.2 subtask 3, we provide an overview of the existing catalogs available in the Netherlands where SSH data can be found. In particular, we discuss ODISSEI and CLARIAH's work to aggregate datasets from various sources for the social sciences and humanities, respectively. We describe the current stage of both portals and outline planned developments, as well as the contribution SSHOC-NL can make to improve the discoverability of datasets. The recommendations for the next steps and future work are informed by previous research on data discovery including a small study conducted by SSHOC-NL Task 2.3 on the findability of cultural heritage datasets.

Data Discovery in the Dutch SSH Domain

Both social sciences and humanities scholars use various kinds of data which can come from a multitude of sources. Data can be collected by researchers themselves, or they can make use of existing data. When reusing data, it can come from previous research published in a repository (e.g. DANS Data Station SSH) or collected by national institutes (e.g. Sound & Vision), governmental organizations, or statistical offices (e.g. CBS). Data may be available through libraries (e.g. KB), museums, through private companies, or derived from social media platforms.

Existing repositories

Many organizations - although not all - that provide data for research have their own ways of making that data findable and informing researchers about the data they offer. [Re3Data](#), the registry of research data repositories, alone lists 40 repositories¹ when filtered on *Humanities and Social Sciences* as subject and *the Netherlands* as a country. Some of these repositories only hold a few records, for instance repositories established for a given study (e.g. the [DHS](#)). In contrast, others can have hundreds, thousands (e.g. [The Language Archive](#)), or even millions of records (e.g. [Sound and Vision](#), [WieWasWie](#)).

It should be noted that not all of the repositories listed in Re3data are comparable. For instance, in some cases, a large institute may have an entry in Re3Data for their institutional repository, while in other cases, an entry may refer to a small repository established for a specific project or study. The definition of what is considered a record or a dataset within

¹ Search performed in november 2024

<https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&subjects%5B0%5D=1&countries%5B%5D=NLD>

such a repository also varies and is often not even provided in the Re3Data overview. It is also noteworthy that many relevant data providers for SSH researchers may not be listed at all within Re3data. For instance, we found entries for some regional archives (e.g. [Regional Archive Tilburg](#)) while it is very likely that many more comparable archives exist which are not included in the Re3data overview.

Despite these limitations, this small exercise illustrates the vast amount of available data, repositories, and providers managing those data. It also makes it clear that providing one overview of all the existing data for the SSH domain, even if it would only be for the Netherlands, is nearly impossible.

However, supporting researchers in finding relevant datasets for reuse is an important ambition that ODISSEI and CLARIAH share. There is some intuitive understanding that it is useful for researchers to find high quality information about available datasets relevant to their field in one environment rather than searching through several different catalogs. Hence, both ODISSEI and CLARIAH have been working on collecting and aggregating information about relevant available data to make them more easily accessible. We will discuss the implementations that ODISSEI and CLARIAH have been working on in the sections below after reflecting on the user experience of data discovery.

User experience of data discovery

An important question to consider is how researchers become aware of existing data relevant for their project which may be available in one of the repositories listed above. Answers to that question inform how data providers can improve the findability of the data they host.

According to a review by Gregory and colleagues (2019), social science researchers may easily locate data from national, publicly funded data sets but struggle to find smaller datasets for reuse. Social science researchers use publications to find data or rely on colleagues and connections to make requests for datasets they know could be relevant. Gregory and colleagues also note that supporting and contextual information is crucial for data reuse, especially for novice researchers. Trust in the data is also listed as an important condition for reuse. Researchers consider whether a dataset has been reused by others when assessing whether the data is fit for reuse.

To complement studies relying on retrospective data, Krämer and colleagues (2021) directly observed the search behavior of a small group of social scientists and conducted semi-structured interviews afterwards. In line with Gregory and colleagues (2019), this study also showed that datasets are often searched through literature and that personal contacts play a role in guiding the search, in particular when initial search is unsuccessful. The researchers further found that google had a central role in the search activities and that knowledge of tools that support dataset search was often missing. An important aspect guiding the search was the “research knowledge portfolio” of a user which includes their own publications and datasets as well as their experiences with data from others and information they have received from colleagues. Extensive metadata and documentation was seen as crucial to evaluate quality and relevance of a given dataset, as well the source of the data, and reputation of the authors.

Participants perceived various barriers when trying to access data: Data being unavailable and data procedures and rights being unclear were common barriers and there was a general impression that too few datasets are openly accessible. Improvements that were suggested by the participants Krämer and colleagues studied included improving the usability of systems and metadata quality, as well as providing a global aggregated search engine and more domain-specific support, in particular for question and variable searches.

To assess data reuse and infrastructure needs specifically in the context of SSHOC-NL Makhija (2024) conducted a study as part of work package 2.3. The study employed a mixed-methods approach with user interviews and expert consultations in addition to a brief review of existing literature on data discoverability.

The results of this study support the idea that researchers from the SSH domain find available data through various ways including “through projects, universities, talking to colleagues, literature searches, and search engines or other miscellaneous sources such as forums.” Academic institutions played a crucial role in providing access to databases, while professional networks helped guide researchers to relevant databases through shared experiences and recommendations. These findings suggest in line with the studies mentioned above that next to data being published through a repository or local database, providing information about the availability of the data through related publications, projects and peers can be an important entry point to enable discovery and reuse.

The study by Makhija (2024) also assessed the struggles researchers encounter when they want to reuse (cultural heritage) data and provides insights and recommendations to improve the user experience for SSH data discovery. Researchers interviewed in the study reported access restrictions through copyright and difficulties to gain permissions for restricted access data, in line with the results of Krämer et al (2021). Lack of standardization of formats and time-consuming procedures to arrange data to create custom datasets were also reported as limiting factors, as well as incomplete information, inconsistent dataset descriptions and outdated or unavailable registries. Overall, platforms with simple features, clean interfaces, and easy access to collections received positive feedback. Researchers reported that navigating systems required time and, in some cases, technical knowledge. In some cases, expert advice was needed, and a project's success can depend on the availability of this support.

The study identified key needs for positive user experiences in the cultural heritage domain which included having rich metadata and documentation, providing customization options for specific research projects (e.g. dedicated training or data retrieval options customized to a given project) and integrations across data platforms. Furthermore, secure environments for sharing of sensitive data were listed as well as providing user support (e.g. through quick start guides for new users).

(Meta)data Portals in SSHOC-NL

As mentioned above both ODISSEI and CLARIAH want to facilitate the discovery and reuse of available data within their domain. To do this, both have been working on portals that aggregate metadata from various available repositories. ODISSEI makes aggregated metadata of social sciences datasets, available at several Dutch data providers, findable in the ODISSEI Portal. CLARIAH collects metadata from the CLARIN repositories and the NDE heritage dataset register, feeding them into the CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset registry, which then feeds into the Ineo Portal as the user interface.

Below we outline the goal and development of these two Portals as well as their current state and future plans.

ODISSEI Portal

The goal of the [ODISSEI Portal](#) is to provide metadata from datasets which are interesting for (Dutch) social science researchers. The Portal currently has over 10.000 records with metadata from CBS microdata, LISS panel, Dutch social sciences data available at DANS through the DANS Data Station SSH and at DataverseNL, the Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN), and from the Consortium of Individual Development. The focus of the Portal is primarily on quantitative social sciences data and aims to also make metadata available from datasets that require specialized access environments such as the CBS microdata.

The Portal was initially launched as a prototype in September 2022 and improved through multiple updates until the final version of the Portal was launched in December 2024. In 2024 the Portal attracted around 230 unique visitors each month².

The software that is used for the Portal is [Dataverse](#), an open-source repository software developed by Harvard University and used by many repositories including DANS and the DataverseNL community. The general workflow through which metadata is ingested is illustrated in Figure 1. The technical development of the Portal is described in more detail on the [ODISSEI Portal Github](#) where we share the setup of the [Dataverse environment](#) as well as the [ingestion process](#) managed by the workflow orchestrator.

² Visitor numbers were discussed during a webinar presenting the final version of the ODISSEI Portal in december 2024: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14516199>

Figure 1. Schematic of the steps performed to get metadata from a (meta)data provider into the ODISSEI Portal. We extract (yellow), transform (green) and load (blue) information into the Portal.

Metadata Requirements

Metadata from each provider is retrieved, in most cases through an OAI-PMH harvester, and stored. Then metadata is mapped onto a common format. To this end, ODISSEI has specified [minimum metadata requirements](#) for all data providers. Wherever possible metadata is mapped onto common fields which are based on Dataverse metadata blocks which again map to international standards including DataCite, DublinCore and DDI – the latter specifically for the social sciences information.

Enrichments and FAIRness

Before the metadata is imported into the Portal, an enrichment is performed. Through this pipeline, we aim to enrich the metadata with controlled vocabularies or information available elsewhere that can be relevant to the user.

In the current version of the Portal, for instance, metadata is enriched with terms from the [ELSSST](#) controlled vocabularies, a standardized and multilingual list of terms used in the social sciences domain and hosted and promoted by [CESSDA](#).

While the metadata requirements, standardization and enrichment efforts contribute to the FAIRness of the (meta)data, ODISSEI does not currently structurally evaluate the FAIRness or data quality of the incoming metadata.

User interface

The metadata that is harvested is imported into the ODISSEI Portal where the user can search and view the records (see Figure 2). The functionalities of the Portal are described in detail in the [ODISSEI Portal user guide](#) together with additional information about the available metadata fields and their provenance for each Metadata Provider.

Figure 2. Website of the ODISSEI Portal where users can search for data and view the metadata records.

Harvesting harmonized metadata

An important aspect of the ODISSEI Portal is that the Dataverse environment allows for the metadata, once imported in the Portal, to be harvested in turn by third parties and in various metadata formats. The metadata can for instance be made available in schema.org JSON-LD format. This way, the metadata can be made available for an ODISSEI or SSHOC-NL Linked Data Graph which is work conducted through SSHOC-NL Task 4.1.

CLARIAH Dataset Registry

For finding datasets available in the CLARIAH community, users can visit [Ineo](#). Ineo is an interface that combines information about different digital humanities resources including data and tools. For this deliverable we focus on the datasets that are findable through Ineo.

Ineo was launched in June 2024 and at the time of writing almost 14.000 dataset records were included in Ineo.

As can be seen in Figure 3, the information that is fed into Ineo comes from the [CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset Registry](#) which in turn harvests metadata from two sources: CLARIN partners and Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed (NDE).

Figure 3. Schematic of the steps performed to get metadata from one of the partners into the CLARIAH registry and Ineo.

Metadata Requirements

CLARIN-route

CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) partners which are CLARIN B or C centers in the European CLARIN network can provide metadata to CLARIN's central catalog: the [Virtual Language Observatory](#). The VLO has a standardised procedure to harvest metadata describing resources using an OAI-PMH protocol, preferably in [CMDI](#) format. Metadata from the different partners is in this way standardised in the CLARIN VLO. The CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset Registry is a separate instance of the CLARIN VLO. Data providers which follow the CLARIN route into the CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset Registry, similarly have their metadata harvested according to the OAI-PMH protocol, in CMDI format.

NDE-route

The Network Digitaal Erfgoed (NDE, Dutch Digital Heritage Network) has a dataset registry to which partners of the NDE, all of them being cultural heritage institutions, can provide their metadata (dataset descriptions). The NDE thus aggregates metadata from various data providers within their registry. The metadata requirements that the NDE sets are specified [here](#) and include required elements such as a dataset name, publishers, licence and identifier. The metadata should be made available to the NDE registry in RDF. Both the Schema.org and DCAT vocabularies may be used but the use of schema.org is [recommended](#).

The NDE Dataset Register offers two access points: a REST API and a SPARQL endpoint through which information can be accessed.

Further development of the NDE-route into the CLARIAH Dataset registry is part of the SSHOC-NL project under task 2.3.

CLARIAH FAIRy Requirements

As outlined above and illustrated in Figure 3, the CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset registry harvests from CLARIN and NDE. The CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset Registry is an instance of the VLO, which harvests metadata from a specific set of organisations, including a selection of the linguistic research repositories harvested by the CLARIN VLO, but also DANS and the NDE. The [harvesting pipeline](#) and FAIR assessment (see below) is hosted and maintained by the KNAW Humanities Cluster (HuC). At the time of writing, the FAIRy Dataset Registry had not adopted

an overarching set of requirements beyond the CLARIN and NDE requirements. Within SSHOC-NL, however, discussions are being held to come to an agreement on a minimal set of metadata required for the FAIRy Dataset Registry, as well as an RDF-based schema and vocabulary for expressing those metadata.

Enrichments and FAIRness

Before metadata is further fed into Ineo and presented to the user, CLARIAH has implemented a FAIR assessment of the metadata. The FAIR assessment is based on a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP)³ that describes the FAIR implementation choices based on the [CLARIN B centre requirements](#). Using this FIP, a FAIR assessment framework called [pyFAT](#) was created. The current version assesses the CLARIN metadata records and there are plans to develop this further (see below) to produce a score for each metadata record ingested in the FAIRy registry.

Another element in the pipeline is that [Rich User Content](#) (RUC) can be added to the metadata records. This content includes various curated texts pertaining to resources which are then accessible to users exploring a dataset in Ineo.

Figure 4. Website of Ineo where users can search for available data.

User interface

As mentioned above the user can search for the metadata in Ineo (see Figure 4). Ineo allows users to search, browse, find and select digital resources. This includes metadata of datasets, but also includes information about tools, workflows, standards and educational material. Hence Ineo has a broader scope than the ODISSEI Portal which focuses specifically on metadata of datasets. Within the ODISSEI infrastructure there are other components (e.g.,

³ The FIP that was used is included in the supplementary materials of the conference paper research paper titled Comparing FAIR Assessment Tools and Their Alignment with FAIR Implementation Profiles using Digital Humanities Datasets available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261773>

the ODISSEI code library, the SoDa tutorials, the ODISSEI Zenodo community etc) that aggregate resources other than datasets. Part of SSHOC-NL is dedicated to link the various resources and make them more findable collectively (e.g., via the ODISSEI Knowledge Graph).

Harvesting harmonized metadata

Ineo functions only as the front-end of the data discovery platform of CLARIAH and the harvesting and harmonization of metadata is performed in the CLARIAH FAIRy Dataset registry. This harmonized metadata is currently not exportable.

Future directions in SSHOC-NL

SSHOC-NL started in 2024 to bring CLARIAH and ODISSEI closer together to combine forces in providing FAIR data and services to the Dutch SSH community.

Within the FAIR workstream of SSHOC-NL one focus area is to further develop the data discovery facilities, improve the available metadata that researchers can find to evaluate the usefulness of available data and ensure that the obstacles to reusing data are being minimized.

One aspect of this work is to further develop the available data discovery infrastructure that has already been established by ODISSEI and CLARIAH. We aim to learn from each other and adapt successful implementations.

Below we outline a couple of areas which have already been identified as future work within SSHOC-NL. In the coming months of SSHOC-NL these starting points will be taken up further by the task group on Secure data workflows which combine expertise from task 1.1, 2.3 and 4.1 and 4.2 as well as through discussions in the SSHOC-NL Working Group on FAIR implementation which was established by Task 4.1 and 4.2 but invites a broad range of tasks from across the SSHOC-NL project.

Harmonizing across ODISSEI and CLARIAH

Until SSHOC-NL, the development of the data discovery infrastructure has taken place through separate projects and funding streams. The collaboration between the two infrastructures in SSHOC-NL provides the opportunity to assess how efforts can be further combined. We want to assess which elements of the data discovery process could be harmonized and where collaborative development of software could be realized.

While we recognize the difference in metadata standards and the variety of data that is available in the SSH domain, we aim for a closer collaboration on issues that span the entire domain. One option could be that metadata from ODISSEI will become available in CLARIAH or vice-versa. Another option is that the metadata of both will become jointly available through the European Open Science Cloud, for instance the SSHOC-EU Marketplace.

SSHOC-NL facilitates further discussions around this topic across different tasks involved in the data discovery infrastructure at ODISSEI and CLARIAH with a particular focus to include the perspective of the users of the infrastructure.

Managing access to secure data: Data Access Broker

One issue that concerns a great part of the SSH domain is the access to secure data, i.e. data that needs to be protected and can only be accessed in a secure environment and under specific conditions. Such datasets play a role both in the social sciences and in the humanities and there is a large interest in investing in common infrastructure to deal with this use case. An important step has been made in the development of [SANE](#) (Secure Analysis Environment) - which will also be further developed as part of Task 1.1 in SSHOC-NL.

In terms of data discovery, metadata about data access procedures plays a crucial role for making sensitive data discoverable and reusable. Working on the standardization of access conditions and procedures and documenting such conditions in a machine-readable way is a crucial next step. Initial steps have been taken already, for instance through the organisation of a workshop on [ODRL](#) (Open Digital Rights Language) where partners from different SSHOC-NL tasks were present. Building upon this work together will be an important task for SSHOC-NL to improve the FAIRness and discoverability of sensitive data.

Metadata enrichments

The ODISSEI Portal already includes a pipeline to enrich metadata with information from controlled vocabularies. This pipeline provides opportunities for more enrichments than currently applied which will be investigated in the SSHOC-NL project. Furthermore, the enrichment process is also interesting for the metadata in the CLARIAH infrastructure.

FAIR assessments

Conversely, the CLARIAH infrastructure already includes a FAIR assessment of the harvested records. As mentioned above improvements to the current tool are being envisioned (e.g. through the OS-TRAILS project) and the FAIR assessments of records is also interesting for the metadata in the ODISSEI infrastructure.

Sustainability of the available infrastructure

Both ODISSEI and CLARIAH are invested in keeping the existing portals up to date and maintaining the metadata they provide to the community.

This includes ensuring that the metadata that is provided by the data providers moves smoothly through the system and that potential new providers can be easily onboarded. Software updates need to be performed, and support needs to be provided when bugs are being discovered, or users need help in using the system.

The front-end of the CLARIAH infrastructure, Ineo, is currently built on proprietary software managed by an external company. The preference is to replace the front-end by an open source solution which is currently being investigated.

In summary, the coming period within SSHOC-NL will build on the existing data discovery portals in ODISSEI and CLARIAH, taking next steps to align and further develop the available infrastructure. We aim to learn from each other's implementation and tackle common challenges to improve the availability and findability of data for scholars across the SSH domain.

References

Gregory, K., Groth, P., Cousijn, H., Scharnhorst, A. and Wyatt, S. (2019), Searching Data: A Review of Observational Data Retrieval Practices in Selected Disciplines. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 70: 419-432. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24165>

Krämer, T., Papenmeier, A., Carevic, Z. et al. Data-Seeking Behaviour in the Social Sciences. *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, 22: 175–195 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-021-00303-0>

Makhija, K. (2024). Findability of Cultural Heritage Datasets. Research Report. https://hbo-kennisbank.nl/details/sharekit_ahk:oai:surfsharekit.nl:f7744f63-bf9c-4d35-8edd-af95821f95b0

Makhija, K., de Gruijter, M., Keilbach, J. & Raaphorst, M. (2025). Findability of Cultural Heritage Datasets - Summary of research report. <https://zenodo.org/records/14778193>